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Information and Communications Technology (ICT) - Based Learning: Basis for Action Plan

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Abstract

In the dynamic realm of education, technology has emerged as a catalyst for transformative learning experiences, ushering in a new era of technology-based learning. This study, employing a descriptive-correlational research design, delves into integrating technology in education and its impact on learners' science performance. It also scrutinizes the interplay of socio-demographic factors. A sample of 110 learners from selected schools in Balo-I East District participated in the study during the 2023-2024 academic year. Findings reveal a diverse socio-demographic profile, emphasizing the dominant age group of 13-14 years and a balanced representation of genders. Moreover, the socio-economic landscape indicates a middle-income concentration, with smartphones prevalent among families, suggesting potential accessibility to technology. Survey results demonstrate a positive perception of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in learning, especially in science classes, coupled with a high level of science performance among respondents. However, the study unveils a non-significant relationship between science performance and the perception of ICT use, highlighting the complexity of academic outcomes. Based on these findings, recommendations are proposed, including professional development for teachers to enhance technological proficiency, fostering student engagement through interactive digital platforms, promoting awareness of technology-based learning among learners and parents, and suggesting avenues for future research to further explore the relationship between technology awareness and science performance. This study provides valuable insights into the evolving educational landscape and informs strategies to optimize technology integration for enhanced learning outcomes.

Keywords: *information and communications technology, action plan, learners' science performance*

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of education, technology has become a powerful catalyst for transformative learning experiences. The integration of technology in education has given rise to a paradigm shift, fostering a new era of learning known as technology-based learning. This innovative approach leverages digital tools and platforms to enhance traditional educational methods, creating a dynamic and interactive learning environment.

One of the most effective teaching methods is integrating ICT into lessons taught in the classroom. The aim is to enhance a collaborative and constructivist educational process. This is believed to be the appropriate method for education in the 21st century. The Department of Education issued a memorandum no. 78 series of 2010 on the guidelines in the implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP), which aims to provide public schools with appropriate technologies that would enhance the teaching-learning process and meet the challenges of the 21st century.

The integration of ICT in teaching and learning aims to develop highly and internationally competent learners. The transition from teacher-centric to student-centric training is supported by ICT. Role-playing, team problem-solving exercises, and developed initiatives were all made possible by the cooperative training that was also used. Web-based discussions that are actively replacing traditional academic activity. It encompasses various technologies to expedite the capture, communication, collection, analysis, storage, and distribution of information required for specific tasks (Pedagoo, 2020).

Information and communications technology (ICT) is important to the science curriculum. The use of information and communications technology (ICT) in the classroom encourages learning environments that are more concentrated on the students. However, as the world quickly transitions to digital media and information, information and communications technology (ICT) is playing an increasingly significant role in education and will continue to do so throughout the 21st century (Alvarez, 2020).

According to Andoh (2019), educational institutions can use ICT to give students the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in the 21st century. In doing so, they can increase global access to education, educational equality, the broadcasting of high-quality teaching and learning programs, the professional development of teachers, and the ability to manage education more efficiently. As a result, the internet has become an essential instrument in today's information-driven society, and the idea of a world without it is beyond imagination.

Currently, non-traditional teaching tools like laptops, measuring devices, and personalized high-tech aids are connected to the 21st-century science classroom. It was always believed that using these innovations would fundamentally result in a progressive rebuilding of the teaching and learning process (Paje et al., 2021). It was important to properly understand the views and perspectives of the students and teachers before initiating any endeavor, as they were the two groups that stood to gain the most from any attempt to integrate technology into schools (Quing, 2017). Computers made the teaching-learning process more relevant for the learners, wherein it was connected to real-life situations. It has affected every part of schoolwork, including administration, timetable, project work,

assessment, lesson delivery, and the examination system, etc. It is generally acknowledged as a contemporary tool that enables educators to change their instructional strategies in order to better students' interests.

According to Paje et al. (2021), it is impossible to ignore the value of new technology in schools, especially for science, as its use is likely to benefit science education and learning by advancing and enhancing the production of work; supporting the development of collaborative knowledge; supporting investigation and experimentation; giving students greater responsibility and control through individual investigation and experimentation; and advancing inspiration and commitment. Furthermore, he discovered that science student-teachers who were more proficient with educational technology had greater desires to use it, increasing the likelihood that their students would use it and elevating their social value.

Despite the numerous studies conducted on educational performance, there remains a significant research gap in understanding the specific factors contributing to the low science performance of students in Balo-I East district. While general factors affecting academic achievement have been explored, there is a lack of focused research that delves into the unique challenges and contextual elements influencing science curriculum outcomes in this particular school setting. Identifying and addressing these specific gaps is crucial for the development of targeted interventions and improvements in science subject at the aforesaid school, ultimately contributing to enhanced science performance among students.

Therefore, since science and technology are always related, incorporating technology into teaching is one of the most effective ways to teach science. Teachers and students will benefit much from this. A support for teachers in a method that would help them engage students' interests, which could result in greater learning for the students, a support for students to have experience and to dispel ignorance, which is very useful in the era of computer technology. The value of using a computer, which can eventually be used to improve teaching skills and professionalism in general, must be embraced by teachers who are receptive to this approach.

With the tremendous result above mentioned the researcher aimed to determine the perception of the learners on the use of ICT-based in learning Science among Grade 7 learners. Thus, the researcher would propose an action plan for the teaching and learning enhancement of this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perception of the learners on the use of ICT-based in learning Science among Grade 7 learners. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of,
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. monthly family income; and
 - 1.4. gadgets commonly used at home?
2. What are the respondents' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning science as to,
 - 2.1 level of technology-based integration for students' learning; and
 - 2.2 adequacy of technology-based resources?
3. What is the science performance of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' socio-demographic profile and their science performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between students' perception on the use of ICT in learning science and their science performance?
6. Which of the socio-demographic profiles and perception on the use of ICT significantly predict in the science performance of respondents?
7. What action plan can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods to be used in the study. It also discussed the research design, research environment, respondents, sampling procedures, research instruments and their validity, data gathering procedures, and the statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research was used to describe the socio-demographic profile in terms of age, sex, monthly family income, gadgets commonly used at home, the perception, and performance of the learners. Furthermore, this is a correlational study since the Science performance of the respondents was correlated to socio-demographic profile and the perception on the use of ICT-based in learning Science.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 110 learners in selected schools in Balo-I East District, specifically in Abaga Integrated School,

Cadayonan Integrated School and Sigayan Integrated School during the School Year 2023-2024. The researcher used the Raosoft calculator and simple-random sampling in determining the actual number of respondents of the study. A summary of the distribution of respondents by grade level is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of learners – respondents per school*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Total Number of Learners</i>	<i>Actual Number of Respondents</i>
Abaga Integrated School		30
Cadayonan Integrated School		45
Sigayan Integrated School		35
TOTAL		110

Instruments

This study utilized an adapted questionnaire that was patterned after the two-component model of ICT instruction proposed by Taler and Dullen (2008). The study used two kinds of instruments which were divided into two parts. The first part is the socio-demographic profile and Science performance of the respondents. The second part of the questionnaire was about the level of technology-based integration for students' learning and the adequacy of technology-based resources.

Procedure

The researcher requested assistance in administering and retrieving the questionnaires and personally facilitated the conduct of the study. The Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisor, principal, and teachers of the school gave their permission for the research to be conducted, which facilitated the gathering of data. The researcher discussed and explained the vital parts and mechanics of how to answer some parts of it. The confidentiality of their answers was guaranteed by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

The data was tabulated and interpreted to acquire the actual information needed. The following were the statistical tools used in the treatment and analysis of data.

For problems 1 and 3, Frequency count and Percentage were used in identifying the profile and the science performance of the respondents.

For problem 2, Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) were used in determining respondents' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning science as to level of technology-based integration for students' learning and adequacy of technology-based resources.

For problem 4, Chi-square Test was used to investigate the significant relationship between the respondents' socio-demographic profile and their science performance.

For problem 5, Pearson's r Correlation was used to test the significant relationship between the students' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning Science and their Science Performance.

For problem 6, Regression was used to examine the variables that best predict Science performance of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, monthly family income; and gadgets commonly used at home?

Table 2. *Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
11 – 12	38	34.5
13 – 14	65	59.1
15 - 16	7	6.4
Total	110	100.0

Table 2 presents the age of the respondents. The result showed a notable concentration of respondents in the 13-14 age group, constituting 65 or 59.1% of the total sample. This age bracket, marking the transition from primary to secondary education, reflects a critical developmental period. The prevalence of this age group suggests a vital stage in students' cognitive and emotional growth, warranting tailored educational approaches and support programs.

On the contrary, the 15-16 age category represents the smallest percentage at 6.4% or 7 respondents, indicating a potential area of underrepresentation. While this subset is limited, it emphasizes the significance of acknowledging individual differences among older students, implying a need for targeted interventions and adaptable learning strategies. Thus, the age distribution underscores the

necessity for nuanced educational strategies that accommodate the developmental diversity among students, recognizing both the dominance of the 13-14 age group and the distinct needs of older students within the sample. In support with the theory of Vygotsky (1978) highlights the role of social interaction in learning. Applying this theory to the 13-14 age group may suggest the importance of collaborative learning and peer interactions during this critical educational phase. In addition, Eccles (2004) as cited by Darling-Hammond (2020) delved into the individual differences among older students and the impact of the educational environment. This study may offer perspectives on the unique needs of the 15-16 age group, supporting the call for targeted interventions.

Table 3. Sex

Sex	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Male	53	48.2
Female	57	51.8
Total	110	100.0

Table 3 displays the sex of the respondents. The result presented a nearly equal representation of male and female respondents, with females slightly outnumbering males at 51.8% compared to 48.2%. This balanced distribution suggests a representative sample, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of gender-related dynamics. The marginal difference in percentages emphasizes the importance of considering gender-specific factors, acknowledging that each gender contributes substantially to the overall sample.

The data also stresses the significance of gender-inclusive educational practices. However, the near equality in numbers does not eliminate the need for gender-sensitive approaches, recognizing the potential for nuanced differences in learning styles and preferences between male and female students. Consequently, this gender distribution emphasizes the necessity for research and educational strategies that encompass the diverse needs and experiences of both male and female students within the analyzed population.

In support of the study of Sadker and Sadker (2018) highlighted the importance of creating gender-inclusive educational environments. The balanced representation of male (48.2%) and female (51.8%) students in your dataset aligns with the principles advocated in this study, emphasizing the need for equitable educational practices.

McQuillan and Leininger (2021) explored gender differences in learning styles, providing insights into how males and females may have distinct approaches to learning. This study may inform the need for tailored instructional strategies that consider the varied preferences within your dataset.

Table 4. Family Monthly Income

Family Monthly Income	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
5,000.00 and below	38	34.5
5,001.00 – 10,000.00	42	38.2
10,001.00 – 20,000.00	23	20.9
20,001.00 and above	7	6.4
Total	110	100.0

Table 4 shows the family income of the respondents. The result presented that the majority of families fall within the middle-income range, specifically in the bracket of 5,001.00 to 10,000.00, comprising 42 or 38.2% of the total sample. This suggests a considerable concentration of families with moderate financial means. Conversely, the lowest income category, encompassing those earning 5,000.00 and below, represents 38 or 34.5% of the respondents, indicating a significant proportion of families facing economic challenges.

On the other end of the spectrum, families with a monthly income of 20,001.00 and above constitute a smaller portion, at 7 or 6.4%. This discrepancy in income distribution may have noteworthy implications for various socio-economic aspects, such as access to education, healthcare, and overall quality of life. This implied that income disparities can influence educational attainment and health outcomes, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address the specific needs of families in lower income brackets. It also underscored the role of income in shaping the overall well-being of individuals and families, reinforcing the significance of policies aimed at reducing economic inequalities for a more equitable society.

In support of the study of Edin & Shaefer (2015) showed the implications of low-income level of 5,000.00 and below and discuss extreme poverty in the United States. For the highest income bracket of 20,001.00 and above, studies on wealth distribution and its impact on societal dynamics could be relevant and provides insights into income and wealth inequality (Alfani, 2021).

Table 5. Gadgets Commonly used at Home

Gadgets	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Smartphone	63	57.3
Laptop	23	20.9
Tablet/Ipad	12	10.9
Speaker	6	5.5
Computer Desktop	6	5.5
Total	110	100.0

Table 5 presents the gadgets commonly used at home by the respondents. The result presented a notable prevalence of smartphones, constituting 63 or 57.3% of the respondents. This high frequency underscores the ubiquitous nature of smartphones in modern households, aligning with the widespread integration of these devices into daily life for communication, information access, and entertainment.

In contrast, laptops, tablets/iPads, speakers, and computer desktops exhibit lower frequencies ranging from 6 or 5.5% to 23 or 20.9%. The dominance of smartphones may signify a shift in the dynamics of technology use, with these handheld devices serving as multifunctional hubs for various needs.

The literature supports this trend, as studies by Katz and Aakhus (2002) on mobile communication and Chinn and Vincent (2018) on the integration of smartphones into everyday life shed light on the transformative impact of smartphones on communication patterns and information consumption. This high reliance on smartphones may have implications for digital accessibility, with considerations for designing technologies that align with users' preferences and practices in an increasingly mobile-centric landscape.

Problem 2: What are the respondents' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning science as to level of technology-based integration for students' learning and adequacy of technology-based resources?

Table 6 presents the respondents' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning science as to level of technology-based integration for students' learning. The result showed varying mean distributions across different indicators. The highest mean, at 3.32, pertains to the agreement that the use of ICT helps in finding related knowledge and information for learning in science class, emphasizing the role of technology in facilitating access to educational resources.

Conversely, the lowest mean, at 2.97, suggests agreement with the statement that students are more behaved and under control with the use of ICT. This discrepancy underscores a potential area for further investigation into the effectiveness of technology in classroom management.

Table 6. *Level of Technology-Based Integration for Students' Learning*

Indicators	Mean	$\pm$	SD	Description
ICT allows us to be more creative and imaginative in science class.	3.26	$\pm$	0.73	Strongly Agree
The use of ICT helps us find related knowledge and information for learning in science class.	3.32	$\pm$	0.66	Strongly Agree
The use of ICT encourages us to communicate more with our classmates.	3.08	$\pm$	0.65	Agree
The use of ICT increases our confidence to participate actively in class in science subjects.	3.10	$\pm$	0.72	Agree
I learn more effectively with the use of ICT in science class.	3.08	$\pm$	0.73	Agree
The use of ICT aids in the expansion of our knowledge in paradigmatic science subjects.	3.01	$\pm$	0.61	Agree
The use of ICT helps to improve our abilities, specifically in reading and writing.	3.11	$\pm$	0.61	Agree
I am more behaved and under control with the use of ICT.	2.97	$\pm$	0.70	Agree
The use of ICT enables us to express our ideas and thoughts better in science class.	3.03	$\pm$	0.74	Agree
The use of ICT promotes active and engaging lessons for our best learning experience in science class.	2.98	$\pm$	0.62	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.10	$\pm$	0.38	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree 1.75-2.49 Disagree 2.50-3.24 Agree 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The literature by Ertmer (1999) and Puentedura (2006) supports the positive impact of technology on learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of integrating ICT for improved access to information and enhanced learning experiences.

However, research by Hall and Higgins (2005) as cited by Obe (2018) also indicates the need to consider the contextual factors affecting the use of technology in classrooms, including its influence on student behavior. These findings suggest a nuanced relationship between technology integration and student engagement, highlighting the necessity for a comprehensive approach to leverage the benefits of ICT in education.

Table 7 presents the respondents' perceptions on the use of ICT in learning science as to adequacy of technology-based resources. The result showed varying mean distributions across different indicators. The highest mean, at 3.08, indicates agreement with the availability of a sufficient variety of specialized software and educational apps for different subjects, highlighting the importance of diversified digital tools for an enriched learning experience.

Similarly, the lowest mean, at 2.66, suggests agreement that the ICT facilities in the school are well-functioning and can be used in science class. This lower mean underscore potential challenges with the functionality of existing ICT infrastructure. The literature by Moersch (1995) emphasizes the significance of a variety of software and apps in enhancing learning experiences, aligning with the findings of the high mean indicator.

On the other hand, studies by Oladele (2021) discussed the importance of reliable and well-functioning technology infrastructure for effective integration in the classroom, supporting the interpretation of the lower mean. The overall weighted mean of 2.89 indicates a general agreement regarding the adequacy of technology-based resources, suggesting a positive foundation for further enhancements while also highlighting the need for addressing specific challenges, particularly related to the functionality of existing ICT facilities.

Table 7. *Adequacy of Technology-Based Resources*

Indicators	Mean	$\pm$	SD	Description
The ICT facilities in my school are well-functioning and can be used in science class.	2.66	$\pm$	0.78	Agree
I encounter difficulties in the science class, technical assistance is provided by the teacher.	2.96	$\pm$	0.66	Agree
Little access to ICT prevents me from using it in science class.	2.92	$\pm$	0.69	Agree
Lack of support from the school's top management discourages me from using ICT.	2.73	$\pm$	0.75	Agree
I learn more effectively with the use of ICT in science class.	3.03	$\pm$	0.71	Agree
Science classes are not enough for me to use ICT for the learning process.	2.77	$\pm$	0.92	Agree
There is a sufficient variety of specialized software and educational apps available for different subjects.	3.08	$\pm$	0.69	Agree
I am more behaved and under control with the use of ICT.	3.10	$\pm$	0.65	Agree
The ICT resources adequately support interactive and collaborative learning experiences.	2.70	$\pm$	0.83	Agree
Students are given more time to learn and be comfortable with the use of ICT in teaching science.	2.99	$\pm$	0.71	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.89	$\pm$	0.36	Agree

Problem 3: What is the science performance of the respondents?Table 8. *Science Performance of the Respondents*

Performance Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
90 – 100	8	7.3	Outstanding
85 – 89	58	52.7	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	41	37.3	Satisfactory
75 – 79	3	2.7	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	0	0	Did not meet expectation
Total	110	100.0	

Table 8 presents the science performance of the respondents. The result revealed a distribution across various performance ranges. The highest mean, at 52.7%, corresponds to the "Very Satisfactory" range, with scores falling between 85 and 89. This suggests a substantial majority of students performing well in science. Conversely, the lowest mean pertains to the "Fairly Satisfactory" range, with only 2.7% of students scoring between 75 and 79.

While the absence of scores below 75 indicated a commendable overall performance, the concentration in the "Very Satisfactory" range implied an opportunity for further improvement and differentiation in academic achievement.

The literature by Tao et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of constructive feedback and targeted interventions for students within the "Very Satisfactory" range to enhance their learning outcomes. Additionally, studies by Black and Wiliam (1998) as cited by Darling-Hammond (2020) highlighted the significance of formative assessment practices in improving student achievement, providing a framework for educators to address specific learning needs. The presented distribution offers a nuanced perspective on science performance, suggesting a need for tailored educational strategies to elevate students from the "Very Satisfactory" to the "Outstanding" category, ultimately fostering continuous academic growth.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between respondents' socio-demographic profile and their science performance?Table 9. *Relationship Respondents' Science Performance and Socio-demographic Profile*

Variables	Science Performance		Remarks	Decision
	X^2 (df)	p-value		
Age	28.796 ^{ns} (22)	0.151	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Sex	34.362 ^{***} (11)	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0
Monthly family income	40.670 ^{ns} (33)	0.168	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Gadgets commonly used at home	37.917 ^{ns} (44)	0.729	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0

Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 9 displays the relationship between respondents' socio-demographic profile and their science performance. The result showed that the respondents' science performance had a significant association with their socio-demographic profile in terms of sex. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' teaching performance and the demographic profile were not rejected as to age, monthly family income, and gadgets commonly used at home, while sex was rejected. This indicates that gender differences play a role in shaping science academic outcomes among the respondents.

The literature on gender and academic performance, such as study by McQuillan and Leininger (2021), supported the notion that gender-related factors can impact academic achievement. This information suggests the importance of considering gender-specific educational strategies to enhance science performance. While age, monthly family income, and gadgets used at home might not be influential factors, recognizing and addressing gender-related disparities could be crucial for promoting equitable educational outcomes

in science.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between students' perception on the use of ICT in learning science and their science performance?

Table 10. Relationship1 Respondents' Science Performance and Perception on the use of ICT

Variables	Teaching Performance		Remarks	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
Level of technology-based integration for students' learning	0.032 ^{ns}	0.741	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Adequacy of technology-based resources	-0.069 ^{ns}	0.473	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Pearson's Correlation ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns – $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 10 displays the relationship between students' perception on the use of ICT in learning science and their science performance. The result showed that the respondents' science performance had no significant relationship with the perception of the use of ICT in learning science. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the science performance and the perception of the use of ICT in learning science, was not rejected.

In terms of the level of technology-based integration, the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.032 with a p-value of 0.741 suggests no significant correlation between how technology is integrated into learning and the science performance of the respondents. This implied that, based on the data, the extent to which technology is incorporated into the learning process does not appear to have a discernible impact on science performance.

This finding aligned with study by Asad (2021), which highlight that the mere presence of technology in education does not guarantee improved learning outcomes; rather, its effectiveness depends on how it is integrated into the curriculum.

Similarly, the adequacy of technology-based resources showed a non-significant correlation ($r = -0.069$, $p = 0.473$) with science performance. This implies that, based on the data, students' perceptions of the sufficiency of technological resources do not significantly affect their science performance.

This result aligned with research by Uers (2018), which suggests that while access to technology is essential, its impact on academic performance is contingent on various factors, including pedagogical strategies and teacher support.

In summary, the lack of significant correlations between science performance and both the level of technology-based integration and the adequacy of technology-based resources highlights the complexity of the relationship between technology perception and academic achievement. It underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of how students engage with and perceive the role of technology in their learning experiences.

Problem 6: Which of the socio-demographic profiles and perception on the use of ICT significantly predict in the science performance of respondents?

Table 11. Variables that best predict Respondents' Science Performances

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.119	0.638		3.322	0.001
Age	0.171	0.112	0.150	1.523	0.131
Sex	0.075	0.127	0.057	0.587	0.558
Monthly family income	0.049	0.072	0.067	0.672	0.503
Gadgets commonly used at Home	0.025	0.055	0.045	0.457	0.649
Level of technology-based integration for students' learning	0.115	0.206	0.067	0.557	0.579
Adequacy of technology-based resources	-0.232	0.217	-0.126	-1.067	0.289
	$R = 0.200$	$R^2 = 0.040$	$F = 0.718$	$Sig. = 0.636$	

Table 11 presents the variables that best predict respondents' Science performance. The respondents' science performance was not affected by the socio-demographic profile and the perception of the use of ICT in learning science. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' science performance. The R² value of 0.040 implies that 4.0% of the variance in teaching performance can be explained by the socio-demographic profile and the perception of the use of ICT in learning science. Hence, 96.0% of the respondents' science performance difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.718 with a corresponding p-value of 0.636. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' coping mechanism" was not rejected.

Implications of these findings include the recognition that teaching strategies are multifaceted and may not be solely predicted by demographic or technological variables considered in this analysis. Educators and policymakers may consider a broader range of factors, including pedagogical training, classroom dynamics, and institutional support, when aiming to understand and enhance teaching strategies. Additionally, the non-significant influence of technology-related variables may indicate a need for targeted interventions or training programs to effectively integrate technology into teaching practices. Uerz (2018) had conducted extensive research on the integration of technology in education. Their work emphasizes the importance of teachers' perceptions of technology and the availability of resources in shaping their instructional practices.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated. The importance of tailoring educational strategies to accommodate the diverse developmental needs of students, particularly considering the dominant age group of 13-14 years and recognizing the distinct requirements of older students within the sample. The nearly equal representation of male and female respondents, with a slight female majority, suggests a gender-balanced approach in designing educational interventions. The socio-economic landscape revealed a concentration of families in the middle-income range, with a notable prevalence of smartphones, highlighting the potential accessibility of technology among the sampled population.

The survey results indicate a positive perception of the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in learning, with a high agreement level regarding its contribution to finding knowledge and information in science classes. The acknowledgment of a sufficient variety of specialized software and educational apps for different subjects emphasizes the importance of diversified digital tools for an enriched learning experience.

Furthermore, the majority of respondents fell within the "Very Satisfactory" range in terms of science performance, suggesting a generally high level of achievement. The association between science performance and socio-demographic profiles, particularly sex, suggests potential areas for further exploration and targeted educational interventions.

However, it is noteworthy that science performance did not show a significant relationship with the perception of ICT use in learning science, indicating the need for a more understanding of the factors influencing academic outcomes. Thus, the study revealed a complex interplay of socio-demographic factors, technology perceptions, and science performance, highlighting the multifaceted nature of the educational landscape in the sampled schools during the specified timeframe.

Based on the analysis, findings, and conclusions made on the study, the following recommendations are set forth, to wit: (1) School administrators may provide professional development and training opportunities for teachers to enhance their technological proficiency. (2) Teacher may use of interactive and collaborative digital platforms that foster student engagement and leverage technology to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. (3) The learners may know the importance of technology-based learning and its potential contribution to their science performance. (4) The parents may support and facilitate the utilization of technology-based learning for their children and strengthen the parent-child bond while supporting academic growth. (5) Future researchers may find value in examining the relationship between awareness of technology-based learning and learners' science performance, using this study as a starting point and benchmark.

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